

METHODS OF CONDUCTING FIELD SPECTATIONS

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Annotation: This article provides full information about the specific features of the script of a public theatrical event, the elements of the event, various methods of script writing, and the duties of the director in organizing the event.

Keywords: open field, dramaturgy of an event held in an open field, score, musical rhythmic composition and rearrangement.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена полная информация об особенностях сценария публичного театрального мероприятия, элементах мероприятия, различных методах написания сценария, а также обязанностях режиссера при организации мероприятия.

Ключевые слова: чистое поле, драматургия мероприятия, происходящего в открытом поле, партитура, музыкально-ритмическая композиция и аранжировка.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ommaviy teatrlashtirilgan tadbir ssenariysining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini, tadbirlarning elemntlari, senariy yozishning turli xil me'todlari, rejisyorning tadbirni tashkil etishdagi vazifalari haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ochiq maydon, ochiq maydonda o'tkazilgan tadbir dramaturgiyasi, partitura, musiqaviy ritmik saflanish va qayta saflanish.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts [1]. In particular, on May 30, 2019 “On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21, 2020 [2], “On measures to further increasing the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD-4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” of April 21, 2020, No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” of April 20, 2021, Decree No. PD-6208 of. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek

music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

The task of the director staging a public theatrical event is to determine the stage image solution, the “path” - development of the event, the action of the event (the behavior of the leader), the form, atmosphere and style of the director's work begins with the plan.

As long as the primary element of the upcoming event is not the peso and musical score, but the director's plan, then the director also fulfills the role of dramatist here.

It is logically possible to justify the director's forced performance of such a second task. Because there are still very few professional (specialized) playwrights who understand the specific features of the script of a public theatrical event. Thus, in addition to the main three aspects of the director's duty (teaching of V. I. Nemirovich - Danchenko), staging, education and organization, the director becomes a dramatist (fourth aspect), the creator of the event, the “author of the performance”.

Here are some examples of director's plans that clearly determine the style and form of the event, the behavior of the leader (the behavior of the leader):

A large theatrical event called “Tashkent Evening” was staged in the recreation park as a copy of the “Tashkent Evening” newspaper. The ticket sellers are dressed like newspaper sellers, and the conductors are speaking on behalf of the kiosks (newspaper sellers in the shops). The Kordeballet (a troupe of dancers and dancers who perform mass dances in opera and ballet theater) portrays “Living Letters” and they write the titles of the episodes through the dances and so on. This is the feeling of patriotism and patriotism in this nation is important in formation. [2]

The main impetus for the emergence of a directorial plan is the theme, idea and ultimate goal of the event, the venue, the available creative power and material resources, depending on the given event and place (intended to be held). documents and narratives are clearly given conditions of the event, including traditions and customs.

“Regardless of when a dramatic work (pesa) was written in art institutions, it can be staged if it is found to be appropriate and meets modern requirements. And the script of a public event is written based on the set date for immediate performance. is written”.

Therefore, whoever is engaged in script writing (of course, the director of a public event works more on the script), he should have the following skills:

- a) To be a person who can deeply understand socio-political, cultural life, work and life of the local population and can analyze it correctly;
- b) to be a person who has thorough (fundamental) knowledge in the field of literature, especially dramaturgy, and can use it effectively;
- c) it is necessary to be a creator who can collect vital materials (information) and documentary evidence, and who can describe them in a literary and artistic form.

The plan assigns the director the task of sorting numbers, reviewing them and preparing new ones. Detailed knowledge and preparation of local materials, together with numbers, will help to create a director's plan for the upcoming event based on the intention. And after that, the stage of creating a detailed, directorial literary script begins. This type of classification is mostly related to propaganda and propaganda work in cultural and educational institutions. [3]

A public event should be moving, entertaining, emotional and expressive (imagery). "Speaking" episode consists of scenes without movement - expressive reading (declamation) is strictly prohibited in it. The event consists of symbolic (symbolic) and figurative (metaphors), pictorial mise-en-scenes, interconnected sounds that remind each other, etc. In a word, the event should consist of a system of audio (hearing) and visual (visual) images, replacing dialogues and monologues. This is especially evident when the event is staged in buildings that are not adapted for the performance of traditional performances or in open spaces, because in such places the text is not heard at all. Poetic works created by representatives of classical literature are highly valued by our people as examples of high creativity [4]. At such times, if the director needs to "say" something to the audience, not just a show, he replaces the sounding words with writing. But the words that need to be written, in some cases whole sentences, are written through specific means that only apply to this type of art, that is, specific situations or actions of the participants in the venue, a piece of props. with a flag, artistic playing stands with colored flags, electrotablo (with light bulbs on a plate that shows some information by means of light or electromagnetic), with a special title (words) displayed on big screens, and so on.

So, the basis of the spectacle nature of a public theatrical event is a pantomimic composition with a wide range of dance and music, supported by a small number of words. At the same time, texts should be short, large,

expressive, similar to a poetic verse or a circus reprise (a short comic number). It is necessary to take into account all the above conditions at the scenario stage. In the final stages of creating a screenplay, the director can be assisted by a skilled writer, preferably a poet rather than a playwright or writer.

Although it seems that the above-mentioned points are understandable to everyone, the main mistake in today's public theatrical events is the multiplicity and fake literature in these events. The above should not lead to the idea that speech should be avoided all the time in all types of public theatrical events, sound-amplifying equipment, acoustics (property of sound being heard everywhere in the building) and a good stage it is necessary not to abandon the tried and tested means of expression of the traditional literary theater on the fields or stages (cinema concert halls, green theaters, some sports palaces). However, in such performances, it is necessary not to forget the unique nature of the public event, to make a different ratio between the literary text and the spectacle, not to forget the accuracy of selection and sense of the norm.[5]

Directors looking for a figurative solution to episodes (films) make one more mistake, that is, they replace literary texts with "live scenes" (pictures). Unfortunately, the image outside of the movement does not give the expected effect, without confrontation, without struggle, without an active line of action, a public event becomes a set of well-chosen illustrations (pictures, photos) or, simply put, boring. becomes a spectacle. And this is the destruction of all types of performing arts. Especially for public theatrical performances, such errors can often be seen in theatrical processions (ceremonial or carnival, that is, a large crowd, it doesn't matter). Behavior is replaced by ordinary movement, that is, the passage of the costumed group and decorated cars is carried out. Perhaps such things are not boring, because views and impressions are often exchanged. But still they are slow and motionless. It is not so difficult for each group It should not have its own plot or concert number, behavior, accompanying music. Each car should become a small theater or a pulpit on wheels. The contrast should be within the number or between numbers.

Due to the interest in musical rhythmic formations and re-formations, sports numbers and so on, "theatricalization" disappears in mass events staged in homes by directors (professionals who stage mass gymnastic performances or, simply put, trainers) in homes, only the character related to physical education appearances appear. Usually, such events are organized according to the scheme developed by the Frenchman Pierre de Coubertin for the opening ceremony of the Olympic Games a few years ago, that is, participants and

distinguished guests (delegation - representatives, war and labor, ready-made mold, athlete and dancers, brass band and children's performance, carrying colorful flags by hand or on motorcycles, waiting for the main flag, lighting the fire, leader's speech, folk folklore composition and mass gymnastic performances of athletes that form the main essence of the event.[6] Over the years, this scheme begins to turn into well-known (stamped) methods. For example, the ceremonial march of the participants began to be extended. As a result, the audience's interest in the event decreased. Public gymnastics performances sing with respect the strength and agility of the body, the beauty and precision of the line, of course, this is beauty. But, unfortunately, the expressive and allegorical (metaphorical) nature of the spectacle is lost behind the mass and synchronicity. As a result, theatricalization and symbolism disappeared.

In the solemn ceremony dedicated to the opening and closing ceremonies of the XX Olympiad houses held by I. Tumanov, a major theorist of mass spectacles and celebrations, a great organizer of this field, there were actually theatrical symbolic (symbolic) episodes: a square typical of the ancient Greek era, two One can remember the carts with wheels, the cochins in them sprinkling roses on the heads of the Olympic heroes, the Olympic bear in the artistic background, the Olympic bear flying into the sky in the dark (inflated toy at rest). Such events (of course, on a smaller scale) were staged in many places at that time, and each director sought to make the spectacle full of emotions, action and unambiguously understandable, while searching for an expressive solution to the content.

The image structure of a public theatrical event is born in the process of searching for a meaningful spectacle equal to the line of behavior, the behavior of the event is determined by the opposition, struggle of ideas and clashes of opposing forces within each episode. This dynamic line and its figurative (expressive) manifestation must be considered by the director in advance when creating the script. At this stage, the director who is writing the screenplay needs to deal with the problems of getting a large group of actors in and out. Because there will be no big curtain or "intermission" at the public event, on the contrary, there will be no time for lunch breaks. An excellent solution to these problems is to dramatize the scene changes and make them part of the stage behavior.

For example, let's take the solution of the "War" episode in some political-public theatrical event.

Athletes wearing green tricots (athletes' uniforms) are placed on the home field in such a way that their line-up on the field resembles a contour (without inscription) card of a country.

Large cities of the country are shown with green flags. At that moment, under the sound of music reminding of "invasion, attack and occupation", the "enemies" (athletes in koratikos) enter with straight steps from the north-west and south gates of the house. Each column is arranged in the form of an arrow, that is, a spear. Under the influence of the fierce attack of the enemies, the size of the blank card becomes smaller, the enemies, that is, the black forces occupy two thirds of the building, but after the demonstration of several numbers showing the struggle of the people for freedom and independence, the "black forces" are squeezed out of the gates, the building the field will be occupied by the green ones again.

When we talk about the script of a public theatrical event, we think of a literary work with a broader image and narrative, like a cinematographic script, that is, compared to a traditional play.

Here, "scenario" is just the accepted term. In terms of form, the script is closer to an opera and ballet libretto (a short content of a work, a literary script) or a pantomime script, that is, a specific director's script with detailed and extensive explanatory texts related to the staging, describing actions and events.
[7]

The director writing the script of a public theatrical event needs to find a theatrical audience with the same meaning as the water, to create a plastic (musical, light) image that is equal to the literary image, maybe even stronger than it. Writing a script for a public theatrical event means creating a world of unique images, symbols and allegories, exaggeration (hyperbole) and exaggerated depictions (grotesques), metaphors and memories. Based on the basic rules, it is possible to create a public theatrical event without a single word or sentence. On the other hand, the "literary script" here cannot be literature, no matter how illogical it is, but it is a director's description or statement consisting of a system of noise, light projections, plastic and other images.

Psychologist V. Levy: "Theater fascinates me only through the appropriate form of attitude. From the process of direct communication, a person receives 30 percent of information through words. The rest are actions, gestures, glances, which rise to the level of symbols in the theater.

If this is the situation in the traditional literary theater, what can be said about the public event?! In our opinion, the famous opinion of V. Mayakovsky

can answer this situation: “The theater is not a mirror that reflects something, but a magnifying glass”. That is why there are exaggerations and exaggerations, masks, puppets, and clowns characteristic of folk or square theater. Apart from these, posters and caricatures are also used.

Let's turn to some more examples: Peter Schumann, the head of the progressive power theater “Bread and Puppet” (“Bread and Puppet”) in the USA, staged a scene of the biblical storm (Nukh tufoni) in the play “People’s benevolence about the end”. All the actors are dressed in white linen shirts and pants, lying face down on the ground, slowly moving forward, and Noah is standing on their shoulders, swinging the anchor stick. When he presses the anchor stick to the ground and transfers the weight of his body to the other leg, the white body begins to move forward. Sometimes he jumps from one body to another, as if jumping from ice to ice. In such a situation, these people slowly crawl and float, sometimes settling in one corner of the square, and sometimes in another corner, and the effect of such a mise-en-scène is very great.

“When the stage is filled with a large number of performers, there is a need for expressiveness in the mise-en-scène, which is related to the art of sculpture”, wrote S. M. Eisenstein, a master of figurative mise-en-scène. Also, this idea does not apply to the script, but to the director's staging work. To make it easier to consider this problem in parts, we have artificially divided the concept of an inseparable director and screenwriter into sections. In practice, the director's intention, screenplay, staging work are an inseparable part. Sometimes, first of all, the director constructs pictorial mise-en-scenes with his inner vision. This, in turn, tells the direction of the whole event. After that, a script will emerge from this “matiz”. In the process of creating an artistic image, everything that applies only to this art, that is, mise-en-scenes, decorations, costumes, props, light, music and noises, that is, the art of creating unique means of expression - everything they have the same function and the same meaning. These elements are interrelated, and each of them can serve as a motivation for the director who is writing the script in creating the image of the upcoming public theatrical event.

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